

Instructions to participants

In this experiment, you are going to work with 2 versions of the same metadata-based framework (that uses annotations), one implemented using reflection and other using the Esfinge Metadata API. In each version, you will implement 2 different tasks about introducing code conventions.

A code convention is a way to define metadata which considers characteristics intrinsic to the programming elements, such as its name or type. A code convention can usually be applied to avoid defining explicitly an annotation. As an example, having a method that starts with "test" can define the same as having the @Test annotation.

Look at the line with your name in the spreadsheet available at the link

[https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/144aFbMBQz3-fnrbkNesZJHW\]kOz9sfj8srljKHIMLJE/edit?usp=sharing](https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/144aFbMBQz3-fnrbkNesZJHW]kOz9sfj8srljKHIMLJE/edit?usp=sharing)

to identify the values of the <variables>. The <variables> columns on spreadsheet are <order>, <reflection repo> and <esfinge repo>. **You should have accepted an invitation to 2 github repositories.**

Step 1. Understanding the Framework

Read the documentation about the framework

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Wjza3ZUD1EjRdsEd8Qw3vwk_u7vY0uDq/edit?usp=sharing&oid=109691126815611717486&rtpof=true&sd=true

You can look at this documentation at any time.

Step 2. Defining the order to execute the experiment

If <order> is "reflection->esfinge" go to the Step Reflection first

If <order> is "esfinge->reflection" go to the Step Esfinge first

Read all instructions of the step before proceeding.

Step Reflection.

- 1) Clone or download the repository from GitHub via HTTP,

<https://github.com/Metadata-Experiment/<reflection repo>.git>

or via SSH

```
git@github.com:Metadata-Experiment/<reflection repo>.git
```

where <reflection repo> is the value of the column on the spreadsheet.

- 2) Open the project with your IDE.
- 3) To check if everything is ok run the tests on package `com.pmapper.annotationTests`, all tests must pass.
- 4) The tests on `com.pmapper.conventionTests` are relative to your tasks and don't need to pass at this moment.
- 5) Open the document with the task description in the root folder of the repository named **Task1.pdf AND Task2.pdf**
- 6) Read and understand the task. If you think you will need to study something that you will need for the task, do it now. You can keep this material and consult it at will during the task.
- 7) **When you are ready to begin, start measuring the time.**
- 8) Implement the required functionality. It is considered done when all the tests, including the existing ones and the ones relative to the task, are executed properly. If you create any new class, it should be created in the main source folder (not in the test source folder).

Try to execute the task in a moment so that you don't need to interrupt it in the middle. If, for some reason, you need to interrupt the execution of the task, stop the time and resume only when you return to it. We will ask you in the final questionnaire about this interruption and if you think that it affected the experiment somehow.

- 9) **When all the tests pass, stop measuring the time. Note the resulting time because it will be asked later.**
- 10) If you don't finish after one hour, you should stop and consider it finished. Save the last state of your code.

Please do not change the tests code, your production code should be adapted to the tests

- 11) Commit the code only after you finish, both after one hour or if you were able to execute all the tests.

If you did this one first, proceed to Step Esfinge. Else, go to the Final Step.

Step Esfinge.

- 1) Read the documentation about the Esfinge metadata API at
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1inUD97gRM8icpexud3TguPPoR-LbyOTQ/view?usp=sharing>
- 2) Clone or download the repository from GitHub via HTTP,
`https://github.com/Metadata-Experiment/<esfinge repo>.git`
or via SSH
`git@github.com:Metadata-Experiment/<esfinge repo>.git`
where <esfinge repo> is the value of the column on the spreadsheet.
- 3) Open the project with your IDE.
- 4) To check if everything is ok run the tests on package `com.pmapper.annotationTests`, all tests must pass.
- 5) The tests on `com.pmapper.conventionTests` are relative to your tasks and don't need to pass at this moment.
- 6) Open the documents with the tasks description in the root folder of the repository named **Task1.pdf AND Task2.pdf**.

You must implement the two tasks using the features from Esfinge Metadata API.
- 7) Read and understand the task. If you think you will need to study something that you will need for the task, do it now. You can keep this material and consult it at will during the task.
- 8) **When you are ready to begin, start measuring the time.**
- 9) Implement the required functionality. It is considered done when all the tests, including the existing ones and the ones relative to the task, are executed properly. If you create any new class, it should be created in the main source folder (not in the test source folder).

Try to execute the task in a moment so that you don't need to interrupt it in the middle. If, for some reason, you need to interrupt the execution of the task, stop the time and resume only when you return to it. We will ask you in the final

questionnaire about this interruption and if you think that it affected the experiment somehow.

10) When all the tests pass, stop measuring the time. Note the resulting time because it will be asked later.

11) If you don't finish after one hour, you should stop and consider it finished. Save the last state of your code.

Please do not change the tests code, your production code should be adapted to the tests

12) Commit the code only after you finish, both after one hour or if you were able to execute all the tests.

If you did this one first, proceed to Step Reflection. Else, go to the Final Step.

Final Step

Go back to the questionnaire and answer about your experience in the experiment. Please, don't forget to describe any relevant fact that happened during the experiment in the open questions.